

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 5.5

Operational workflows for integration of citizen-observed data in authoritative systems

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Operational workflows for integration of citizen-observed data in authoritative systems
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Short Description:
This deliverable presents a workflow to integrate authoritative LULC and citizen-observed data in order to update the authoritative LULC data. The approach is based on data fusion techniques. Each type of citizen-observed data is modelled as a source of information (one data set for each type of data), and pieces of information are fused by using Dempster-Shafer Theory. The workflow is tested for the update of authoritative LULC data produced by IGN-France by integrating citizen-observed data coming from the LandSense campaigns (Demo case 1, Toulouse pilot). Despite the heterogeneity and the limited amount of citizen-observed data sets used here, the results are promising and show the potential in using citizen-observed data to update or potentially enrich authoritative LULC data.
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1 Introduction: the needs and production of LULC data

This deliverable focuses on how citizen-observed data can be integrated with authoritative data and help to advance Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) mapping.

In Europe, many efforts have been made to provide Earth Observation data (e.g., from Sentinel satellites) or to produce authoritative LULC data. At a European level, examples of LULC initiatives in the framework of Copernicus include the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) inventory and the development of the Urban Atlas (UA) data set. At a country level, LULC mapping has traditionally been undertaken by an authoritative body such as a National Mapping Agency (NMA). However, the increasing demand for data on LULC at fine spatial and temporal resolutions cannot be met by authoritative agencies as they do not have the resources required to collect and process the information.

There is, therefore, considerable interest in using citizen-sensors as a source of LULC information. However, there are numerous challenges in the use of citizen-observed data. First, there is confusion between LULC classes (Comber, 2008). Second, there are different existing nomenclatures for LULC such as CLC (EEA, 2000), UA (EEA, 2011), LUCAS (Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey) (EEA, 2011), INSPIRE (Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community) (EEA 2011) and CNIG (National Council of Geographic Information) (CNIG, 2014), among many others. These nomenclatures are often a compromise between an ideal set of classes and the classes that can be mapped practically (e.g., the ones that can be identified from available data sources other than images). Although some recent efforts have focused on establishing links between different nomenclatures (Arnold 2013; Fonte et al. 2017; Schultz et al., 2017), choosing the most appropriate LU or LC class and defining the best overall classification remain complex tasks, which are often dependent on individual interpretation. These tasks depend on both the desired thematic level of detail of the nomenclature and on the minimum mapping unit. Third, LULC data are often made available as vector data sets in which the space is divided into non-overlapping polygons that are associated with a class label that describes the LULC. For some LULC databases, LU can be easily distinguished from LC values (e.g., LUCAS; UA; OCS-GE), whereas for others (e.g., CLC), LC and some LC elements are mixed (e.g., LULC class as “dense urban area”). Finally, concerning the temporal resolution, LULC data are often updated at regular time intervals (e.g., every six years for CLC and UA) but this temporal resolution does not always meet users’ needs. Having up-to-date data are, in fact, the second need (after accuracy) identified by users (Olteanu-Raimond et al., 2017). Data that are updated annually are needed for computing annual or multi-year indicators, for instance, for monitoring increases in soil sealing and housing supply, or for agricultural surveys.

The goal of this deliverable is to describe an operational workflow for updating authoritative LULC data by integrating citizen-observed data coming from the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP). The proposed approach focuses on the Toulouse pilot from Demo Case 1 “Monitoring urban and rural landscape changes” reported in earlier Deliverables (D2.1, D2.2).

Section 2 presents a description of both the authoritative LULC data and the citizen-observed data from the Toulouse pilot. Section 3 describes the proposed workflow. Section 4 presents the results obtained from the Toulouse pilot, which is followed by conclusions and future work in Section 5.

2 Data description

This section describes the data used in the workflow. Two types of data are used: authoritative LULC data produced by IGN-France and citizen-observed data coming from the Toulouse pilot campaign obtained by applying the data collection strategy described in deliverable D2.1. These data are partially presented in deliverables D2.1 and D5.4. However, to provide the necessary context, the main characteristics and needs are presented in more detail here.

2.1 Description of authoritative LULC data and the need for updating

IGN-France (the French National Mapping Agency) has defined specifications for the authoritative LULC database to meet the requirements of the CNIG. The corresponding LULC database is called Occupation du Sol à Grande Echelle (OCS-GE) and it describes the LU and LC of an area. The first release was made in 2016 and concerned a snapshot of the field in 2013 on the Midi-Pyrénées Region (where Toulouse is the main city). A second release made in 2019 concerns the Toulouse urban agglomeration and represents the area in 2016. OCS-GE is an on-demand product. It means that there is no objective for the state to cover every Region¹ in France (contrary to the other databases produced by IGN-France, which cover the entire country). It is produced when a local administrative entity needs this type of database. The production costs are shared between the state, regional and local authorities.

The characteristics of the OCS-GE are as follows:

Data model. OCS-GE is a vector data set in which the terrain is divided into non-overlapping polygons. Each polygon contains both LU and LC values.

Nomenclature. The nomenclature of distinct LU and LC classes is INSPIRE-compliant. It has been defined to take user needs into account as expressed by different stakeholders in a consultation process. In the study area, three hierarchical levels are proposed for LC classes and four hierarchical levels for LU classes. In total, the proposed nomenclature contains 17 LU classes and 14 LC classes although not every combination of LU and LC class, i.e., 17×14 , is possible. The LU and LC classes as well as their combinations are listed in Annex 1.

Mapping. The mapping is made with respect to the data specifications including the nomenclature, rules, and thresholds. The mapping process is carried out in three steps. First, a backbone² is generated from the network of main roads and railways. This provides a structure for the landscape that is relatively long-lasting and ensures the geometric consistency of the data over time. Second, polygons with distinct LU and LC values are computed using a semi-automated process and integrating several authoritative databases (e.g., topographic layers, forest layer, and cadastral layer). Finally, a manual step based on photo-interpretation is undertaken to correct errors and fill in the gaps in terms of LU and LC values.

¹ Region: French administrative division. In France there are 18 regions since 2016.

² The backbone is a spatial high-resolution vector product representing the geometric skeleton (i.e., landscape objects targeted as being stable over time).

Update. OCS-GE data are updated on a three-year cycle corresponding to the time interval of the aerial orthophoto production.

Data availability with respect to Toulouse pilot. Two OCS-GE releases were made available and accessible on a free and open access basis for the test area (see Figure 1): a 2013 snapshot (i.e., LULC data produced with respect to the orthophoto from 2013) and a 2016 snapshot (i.e., LULC data produced with respect to the orthophoto from 2016).

A certain number of challenges, especially related to LU classes, can be highlighted when mapping the authoritative OCS-GE. Indeed, due to the fact that LU values are mainly assigned to polygons using photo-interpretation, it is not always easy to determine the correct LU. Three issues exist:

- The lack of information for some LU classes. For example, due to the lack of information regarding the main function of buildings, the LU classes Industrial (LU2), Commercial and Services (LU3) and Residential (LU5) are grouped into one LU class: LU235. Descriptions of these LU classes are given in Annex 1: Land Use and Land Cover Nomenclature.
- The assignment of the correct LU related to quarry and agricultural activities. Quarries mainly correspond to LC class LC1.1.2.1 (Areas with mineral materials). The LU class, which can be US1.3 (Mining and quarrying), US6 (Not currently used) or US6.2 (Abandoned areas), may be difficult to assign without information about the current state of the quarry, i.e., active, closed or abandoned. In large farming areas composed of vegetation and several types of buildings, the LU class is difficult to assess using photo-interpretation since it depends on the functionality of the buildings (e.g., residential, agricultural, touristic).
- Monitoring changes is a time-consuming and expensive task. Detecting changes with automatic processes and assessing the user's and producer's accuracies (see D5.4) are the main issues. Distinguishing between LU changes, LC changes, or both from seasonal changes (e.g., vegetation changes) is also a difficult task. Moreover, some small changes in the field are not meaningful for LULC mapping; the changes will not impact the LU or LC assignment (e.g., a new house in an agricultural area).

Figure 1. Authoritative LULC data for the Toulouse pilot in the south of France: a) location map and b) zoomed into the study site.

Therefore, the first goal of the Toulouse pilot was to define a set of tools and run campaigns to engage with different communities in order to collect data that would deal with the issues listed above. The second goal was to assess the quality of the data collected (D5.4) and to integrate them into authoritative data to produce the snapshot OCS-GE 2019 (in the current deliverable D5.5).

2.2 Description of the citizen-observed data

Two main campaigns were planned in the Toulouse pilot from 2018 to 2020. In this section, the data collected during the first campaign that took place from mid-2018 until the beginning of 2019 are presented. Two protocols were proposed during this campaign: one in the field, named the *in-situ* campaign, and the second on the desktop, called the validation Web campaign. These campaigns were run in order to gain more knowledge about the current LU of the study site. The tools (i.e., the PAYSAGES mobile-application, the PAYSAGES web-application and the PAYSAGES wiki) and the design of the Toulouse pilot campaign have been described in detail in Olteanu-Raimond et al. (2018) and in deliverable D2.2. For more detailed feedback on the first campaign, see Jolivet et al. (2019).

2.2.1 Citizen-observed data collected during the *in-situ* campaign: *in-situ* data

The *in-situ* campaign was carried out using the PAYSAGES mobile application. The contributors were asked to visit highlighted locations corresponding to features in the authoritative LULC data set and to provide feedback with respect to five goals:

- 1. Add new building information.** For a set of buildings, contributors were asked to fill in their primary and secondary functions, as well as the number of floors. Note that the primary and secondary functions are drawn from the same list of predefined values. The building data are inputs for mapping the LU and LC classes of the OCS-GE.
- 2. Update the status of quarries.** This task focuses on the quarry LU polygons to assess LU class LU1.3 (Mining and quarrying). Contributors were asked to indicate the status of a quarry as active, closed or abandoned. This status allows the mining activity (LU1.3) to be confirmed or to update the LU of the polygons to US6.3 (Not currently used) or US6.2 (abandoned area).
- 3. Update the construction area LU polygons.** This task concerned LU classes containing construction. If the construction work was finished, the contributors were asked to update the LU class, and if necessary, the LC class. The LU and LC values were chosen from a list of predefined values.
- 4. Improve the information about the agricultural LU polygons.** This task dealt with locations classified as agricultural for the LU and woodland herbaceous for LC. The goal was to indicate if the polygon belonged to an agriculture LU type (e.g., a cultivated area) or not (e.g., a residential area).
- 5. Validate detected changes.** Potential changes were provided by the change detection service (CDS) developed within the LandSense project. This service uses an algorithm that computes the differences from Sentinel images at different dates. For the locations where a change was detected, contributors were asked to confirm if the change really occurred at the given location, and if so, to fill in the new LU or LC classes from a predefined list of values.

During the campaign organized between June and October 2018, 277 locations were visited and 331 observations (citizen-observed data) were collected. An observation is defined here as a piece of information collected by a contributor about a location. This means that several observations can be associated with the same location; during the campaign, several contributors collected information about the same locations. Table 1 shows the number of observations with respect to the goals of the *in-situ* campaign described above. Locations corresponding to goal 1 about buildings were the most visited, with 178 observations. These observations were close to each other in the field. The locations corresponding to goals 2, 3, and 4 represent 137 observations in total. Finally, very few locations representing change were visited (14 locations) corresponding to only 16 observations. For this campaign, the contributors were students and staff from local authorities. There were 26 contributors. Contributors participated in one, two or three goals.

Table 1. Number of observations associated with the number of unique locations and contributors.

	Number of observations	Number of visited locations	Number of contributors
Building	178	135	21
Quarry, construction area, and agricultural area	137	128	18
Change validation	16	14	10
Total	331	277	26

The visited locations are mapped in Figure 2. The spatial density of the locations is mapped using a heatmap, which is an interpolation of the point locations as a continuous layer. The heatmap is placed on top of a base map showing the area of the *in-situ* campaign. The redder the values, the stronger the spatial density. Figure 2 shows that the spatial distribution of the observed locations is clustered, with the most visited areas in the southeast of Toulouse and in the surroundings of the cities of Auch and Montauban.

Figure 2. Heatmap showing the locations of the *in-situ* campaign.

2.2.2 Citizen-observed data collected during the validation web campaign: Data from the Change Detection Service

The validation web campaign focused on validating changes from the Change Detection Service (CDS). The campaign was run on a desktop using the LACO-Wiki tool. In total, 748 polygons were detected by the CDS as potential changes from 2016 and 2018. They were classified into four LU classes: residential, industrial, infrastructure, and other. Among the total number of detected changes, the polygons labelled as ‘other’ were first deleted. Then, stratified random sampling was applied by using the map categories as strata (see D5.3). In total, 654 areas were selected as reference polygons for validation by citizens. Figure 3 illustrates the validated changes detected by the CDS with respect to the LU class: 405 changes were residential, 217 were industrial and 32 corresponded to infrastructure changes.

Each detected change was validated by two distinct contributors based on the blind validation method (i.e., the volunteers were not told what type of change but had to select the type from a list). The contributors were asked to validate each CDS polygon by choosing one value among the list of values: residential, industrial, infrastructure and no change. They could also skip an individual validation in case of doubt. The 2016 orthophoto and the 2018 satellite image from Google Maps were provided as base maps to help in the validation task. The validation campaign was carried out at the beginning of 2019 (February and May) involving 55 students and 4 experts. Note that a change could be validated by two students, one student and one expert, but never by two experts. Some preliminary results on the data quality assessment were presented in deliverable D.5.4 but the results of this campaign are presented below.

Figure 3. Overview of the detected changes from the CDS as inputs to a validation session in the LACO-Wiki tool.

Concerning contributor agreement, both contributors agreed on 367 changes (58%) while there was disagreement in the case of 273 changes (42%). Concerning contributor agreement with respect to the CDS, the following results were obtained:

- both contributors agreed where the chosen value was the same as the algorithm: 215 (33%)
- both contributors agreed where the chosen value was different from the algorithm: 166 (25%)
- contributors disagreed and at least one contributor chose the same value as the algorithm: 161 (25%)
- contributors disagreed and neither chose the same value as that detected by the algorithm: 112 (17%).

The accuracies when two contributors agreed (381 observations) are:

- Residential: 87%
- Industrial: 92%
- Infrastructure: 17%

These results must be balanced against the different occurrences of each type of change detected by the CDS, since infrastructure changes represent only 5% of the data set whereas industrial and residential changes represents 33% and 62%, respectively. Generally, we observed that residential and industrial changes were detected well, whereas detected changes representing infrastructure were slightly overestimated (only 17% of the detected CDS changes corresponded to an agreement with the contributors when the two contributors agreed).

3 Description of the workflow for updating authoritative data

The goal is to define a workflow that allows LULC data (at time t_1) to be updated to obtain LULC data (at time t_2) by using different citizen-observed data containing changes that occurred in the period t_2-t_1 . Our hypothesis is that if information exists about the change of a feature, then the updating process can decide whether an update should be made. In contrast, if there is no information, then the feature is not updated, but it does not mean that no change has occurred in the real world.

Citizen-observed data correspond to different types of geometry (points and polygons) and have different ways of expressing the change information. We defined a generic workflow in order to take into account citizen-observed data and to update the authoritative OCS-GE data. To integrate the different data sets and hence potentially different pieces of information about LULC, a data fusion approach using Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST) is proposed. DST is considered here for updating authoritative data by fusing multi-source data because it can manage various values for a final decision and can also provide a confidence related to each value. In the field of geographic information, DST has already been successfully applied to different applications such as data matching (Olteanu-Raimond et al., 2015; Touya et al., 2017), classification (Comber et al., 2007; Yang et al., 2018), land cover validation (Comber et al., 2016) and map matching (Nassreddine et al., 2008; Royer et al., 2000). In the following sections, the theoretical concepts defined in the framework of DST are briefly introduced, and the proposed workflow is then explained step by step.

3.1 Framework of Dempster-Shafer Theory

DST supposes the definition of a finite set of N singleton hypotheses corresponding to the potential solutions of a given problem, which is called the frame of discernment. It is defined as $\Theta = \{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_N\}$, where H_i , $i=1..N$ represents a singleton hypothesis. Let us denote, 2^Θ , the power set of Θ , which represents the set of all possible combinations of the singleton hypotheses belonging to Θ . The power set is defined by:

$$2^\Theta = \{\{H_1\}, \{H_2\}, \{H_1, H_2\}, \dots, \Theta\} \quad (1)$$

where $\{H_i, H_j\}$ is a subset representing the proposition P , representing the fact that the solution of a problem is one of these hypotheses (i.e., either H_i or H_j). A key point of DST is the basic belief assignment corresponding to a function that assigns, to a proposition P , $P \in 2^\Theta$, a value named the mass of belief, denoted as $m(P)$ and which represents how much the source of information believes in it.

A basic belief assignment is a function $m: 2^\Theta \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that:

$$\sum_{P \subseteq \Theta} m(P) = 1 \quad (2)$$

DST offers tools to combine several sources of information such as the Dempster's rule of combination (Dempster, 2007). Equation 3 defines the conjunctive Dempster's rule. Let us consider two sources S_1 and S_2 . Each source supports propositions P with a mass of belief, $m_1(P)$ and $m_2(P)$, respectively. We denote by m_{12} the mass of belief resulting from the combination of the two sources by the Dempster's rule that supports the same proposition P :

$$\forall P \in 2^\Theta, m_{12}(P) = \frac{\sum_{P' \cap P'' = P} m_1(P') * m_2(P'')}{1 - \sum_{P' \cap P'' = \varnothing} m_1(P') * m_2(P'')}, P' \text{ and } P'' \in 2^\Theta \quad (3)$$

This rule defines how to merge several masses of belief to determine a new mass of belief expressing the combination of beliefs coming from different sources of information. Let us mention that the combination of different pieces of belief can generate some conflict, which is represented by the denominator of equation (3). In the Dempster's operator, the conflict is distributed among all combined masses of belief.

After the combination of sources, a decision among propositions is made. Different decision rules are proposed in the literature such as the maximum plausibility or the pignistic probability (PP). For more details, see Smets and Kennes (1994). Here, only the pignistic probability is defined in equation 4 as:

$$\forall PP \in 2^\Theta, PP(A) = \sum_{A \subseteq B} m(B) \frac{|A \cap B|}{|B|} \frac{1}{1 - m(\varnothing)} \quad (4)$$

where $|B|$ represents the number of singleton hypotheses contained in proposition B. The term $\frac{1}{1 - m(\varnothing)}$ is to normalize the pignistic probability.

3.2 Updating authoritative data using Dempster-Shafer Theory

For each feature (e.g., a polygon) from the authoritative LULC data, we are looking to see if there are changes highlighted by different data sources representing validated citizen-observed data. Thus, each feature is characterised by zero, one or more observations coming from data sources as illustrated in Figure 4. For example, a feature in Figure 4-f is characterised by four observations from two data sources: Source 1 and Source 2. The first data source contributes with two observations having the same LU label (i.e., LU2). The second data source contributes with another two observations having two different LU labels: LU2 and LU5.

Figure 4. Illustration of six features characterised by (a) zero, (b,c) one, (d,e) two or (f) more observations coming from data sources

In this deliverable, the OCS-GE authoritative LULC data (see Section 2.1) will be updated, and citizen-observed data coming from the LandSense campaign (in the Toulouse pilot) (see Section 2.2) are used as two independent external data sources. In the next section, we refer to a feature that will be updated as an OCS-GE polygon.

The proposed workflow for updating authoritative data is illustrated in Figure 5. It is composed of three main steps: pre-processing, data fusion and final decision. The input data are analyzed and enriched during the pre-processing step, which includes the calculation of agreement between data that are spatially near to one another, the characterization of spatial overlap, data filtering, and the mapping between the labels. Then, in the second step, the data are fused under the framework of DST. Finally, the update decision is made by comparing the DST-derived results with the 2016 authoritative LULC data from OCS-GE.

Figure 5. The workflow for updating authoritative LULC data based on multi-source fusion.

In the following sub-sections, the last three steps of the workflow are detailed.

3.2.1 Data pre-processing

This step comprises four computations: agreement, spatial overlap, data filter, and mapping between LU labels and the authoritative nomenclature.

Agreement calculation

The citizen-observed data correspond to a location but potentially to several contributors, multiplying the information for each data source. CDS data are validated twice, and several *in-situ* locations may be visited repeatedly. For each detected OCS-GE polygon, the most frequently observed label in the set available for a polygon is allocated to that polygon. In the case of ties, such as four contributors where two say LU1 and two say LU2, the label is decided at random. An agreement value is calculated for the most frequently observed label. To clarify, the agreement here is a simple measure to describe how much contributors agree with the single label aggregated by multiple observations. It is defined as the ratio between the frequency of the label having the highest frequency and the total number of contributions. Thus, the agreement value will be larger than 0, as the frequency must be equal to or larger than 1. The agreement is calculated for each data source and each location. If a location is visited only once, the agreement value is equal to 1.

In the case of Data source 1 (*in-situ* citizen-observed data), let us consider a location which is visited four times and the given labels equal to: US2 (Industrial), US2 (Industrial), US3 (Commercial and services), and US5 (Residential). The label having the highest frequency is US2 and its frequency is two. The agreement is equal to 0.5, and US2 will be regarded as the LU class for the considered location.

In the case of Data source 2 (web citizen-observed data), for each CDS polygon there are three LU labels coming from two contributors and the change detection algorithm. Thus, the agreement is equal to 1 if both contributors agree and the chosen LU label is the same as the one given by the algorithm. The agreement value is equal to 0.67 if contributors disagree and one of them chooses the same LU label as the algorithm or contributors agree and none of the contributors has chosen the same LU label as the algorithm. The agreement value is 0.33 if contributors disagree and none of the contributors has chosen the same LU label as the algorithm.

Spatial overlap. In this step, the overlaps between CDS polygons and OCS-GE polygons are handled. There are cases where a CDS polygon may overlap several OCS-GE polygons. To solve this issue, each CDS polygon that intersects several OCS-GE polygons is split into several parts with respect to the OCS-GE polygon. This process is illustrated in Figure 6, where the dashed polygon represents the initial geometry and location of the CDS polygon and intersects different OCS-GE polygons represented, respectively, in red, light blue and dark blue colours. The output corresponds to six divided polygons as indicated in Figure 6. The agreement value is then transferred from the original polygon to the divided polygons. We make sure that one divided CDS polygon is associated with only one single OCS-GE polygon.

If several divided CDS polygons have the same label within the same OCS-GE polygon, these CDS polygons are spatially merged into a single polygon and the agreement values are averaged. Thus, there are no duplicate change labels for update within the same OCS-GE polygon.

Figure 6. Example of managing overlaps between OCS-GE data and CDS data.

Data Filter. Three filters are defined as: geometry-based, agreement-based, and label-based.

First, we have noticed that the geometry of detected changes is not accurate and that the limits of the change are underestimated, with only one part of the change being detected. Thus, small divided CDS polygons may contain misleading change information. As shown in Figure 7, a new residential building (in green) is detected by the CDS. However, the CDS polygon does not represent the shape of the building very well and a part of it overlaps with the neighbouring road. After the splitting step, there are two small polygons representing residential change for the road, which is obviously incorrect (small polygons highlighted by red circles).

Hence, an area threshold has been implemented to exclude such small polygons. If the area is lower than 10 m^2 or the ratio of the areas of the CDS polygons and the corresponding OCS-GE polygon is lower than 0.001 m^2 , the CDS polygon will not be considered for further processing.

Figure 7. Illustration of small divided polygons overlapping the road containing misleading change information.

Second, the agreement value is used to filter the data. If the agreement of the data collected is lower than a threshold, the data are not used. In the present workflow, the agreement threshold is empirically set to 0.33. Finally, the value of the label is taken into account. If the change label cannot be translated to the OCS-GE model, the corresponding data will also be discarded, e.g., those having labels of “No change” and “I don’t know”.

Mapping LU labels to the OCS-GE nomenclature. The goal is to update the OCS-GE authoritative data; thus, labels assigned by contributors should be translated to the OCS-GE model to be comparable with the authoritative data. For *in-situ* data, the new values are already in the OCS-GE model. For the CDS data, the values are mapped as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Mapping CDS labels into the OCS-GE LU nomenclature

CDS -label	LU class in the OCS-GE nomenclature
Industrial	LU2 (Industrial)
Infrastructure	LU4.1 (Transportation network)
Residential	LU5 (Residential)
No change	none
I don’t know	none

3.2.2 Data fusion via Dempster-Shafer theory

After data pre-processing, DST is employed to fuse the sets of citizen-observed data concerning one location and to decide on the final value to be assigned to the corresponding OCS-GE polygon. In this workflow, two data sources are used for the fusion: CDS data and *in-situ* citizen-observed data. Note that these two data sources are independent, which makes it possible to use DST. Data fusion becomes useful where there are multiple CDS and/or *in-situ* data within the same OCS-GE polygon.

Definition of the frame of discernment. To implement the DST, it is necessary to define the frame of discernment Θ and to calculate the mass of belief for each hypothesis. In the present workflow, Θ is defined as all possible LU codes in the OCS-GE nomenclature (see Annex 1) as shown in equation (5):

$$\Theta = \{LU1.1, LU1.2, \dots, LU2, LU3, LU4.1.1, \dots, LU5, LU6.1, \dots, LU6.3\} \quad (5)$$

After the pre-processing steps, each label of the CDS polygon or *in-situ* location corresponds to a singleton hypothesis. In some cases, the contributions correspond to merged LU classes, for instance $\{LU4.1^3\}$, whereas in the OCS-GE nomenclature, the most detailed classes are $\{LU4.1.1^4, LU4.1.2^5, LU4.1.3^6\}$. For the combined hypothesis, such as $\{LU4.1\}$, it should be replaced by the set of corresponding singleton

³ Transportation network

⁴ Road transport

⁵ Railway transport

⁶ Air transport

hypotheses before applying the combination rule, as shown in Table 3. The {LU235⁷} is to the most detailed LU class in the current OCS-GE nomenclature, although the goal is to be able to do the updates at the finest level of detail, corresponding to {LU2, LU3, LU5}.

Table 3. Mapping between the combined hypothesis and the singleton hypotheses

Combination Hypothesis	Singleton Hypotheses
{LU4.1}	{LU4.1.1, LU4.1.2, LU4.1.3}
{LU235}	{LU2, LU3, LU5}

Mass of belief initialisation. The mass of belief for each hypothesis is defined based on the agreement value (as explained in Section 3.2.1). For the CDS data, the mass of belief for each proposition (P) is calculated by multiplying the agreement by the area ratio, as demonstrated in equation (6):

$$m(P) = Agreement * \frac{Area(CDS)}{Area(OCS-GE)} \quad (6)$$

For *in-situ* data, as the information represents the whole OCS-GE polygon, the agreement value is directly assigned as the mass of belief (i.e., $m=Agreement$). Thus, for each affected OCS-GE polygon, masses of belief for the specific data source are assigned to all possible hypotheses denoted as H_s . Note that Θ is also included to express ignorance, which means that the specific data source cannot be used to determine the best solution. The mass of belief for Θ is calculated by equation (7):

$$m(\theta) = 1 - \sum_{P \in H_s} m(P) \quad (7)$$

Data source combination. Once masses of belief have been initialized, data from different sources are combined for each affected OCS-GE polygon using Dempster’s rule (see Eq. 3).

Decision. The decision is made using the criterion of the maximum pignistic probability. By choosing the pignistic probability, the decision is made only among the singleton hypotheses. The hypothesis with the highest mass of belief is chosen in the present workflow.

Update. To determine if the LU class for a given OCS-GE polygon should be updated for the year 2019, DST-derived solutions are compared to the initial OCS-GE class in the 2016 release. If the DST-derived solution is the same as the initial OCS-GE class, there is no need to update the corresponding polygon in the database. Otherwise, the LU class for the corresponding OCS-GE polygon will be replaced by the DST-derived solution.

If the DST-derived solution belongs to the set of {LU2, LU3 or LU5} and the original class is {LU235}, it means that the database should be corrected by replacing LU235 value with the more specific land use class. In this particular case, the update does not represent a change in the real world but rather an enrichment of the LULC data.

⁷ Industrial, Commercial and services, and Residential

4 Results

The workflow presented in Section 3 is applied to the OCS-GE data from 2016 in order to obtain OCS-GE data for 2019. In total, there are 295 OCS-GE polygons flagged with change by the CDS and *in-situ* data. The approach is applied to these polygons, and the DST-derived solutions are assigned to the corresponding OCS-GE polygon. The distribution of DST-derived solutions is plotted in Figure 8. LU5 (Residential) represents 187 occurrences (60% of assignments). Around 20% of the assignment has the LU2 (Industrial) value. The remaining occurrences concern the LU4 (LU4.1.1, LU4.1.3) and LU 6 (LU6.1, LU6.3) classes.

Figure 8. Distribution of LU classes derived from the DST data fusion process.

The results are manually evaluated by comparing the imagery from 2016 and 2018 for each feature. Google Street View imagery is also considered for LU classes that are hard to identify from overhead imagery. The overall accuracy is 79.3%. F_1 score values for each LU class obtained with manual evaluation are plotted in Figure 9. LU5 (Residential) achieved the best result with a value of 89.9%. LU2 (Industrial) also obtained a good result of 82.1%. F_1 score values for LU1.1 (Agriculture), LU1.2 (Forestry) and LU3 (Commercial and Services) are equal to 0. For LU1.1 (Agriculture), when there is a new building in the agricultural area, it should not affect its LU type as mentioned earlier. However, citizens might not have such knowledge and label it as LU5 (Residential) or LU2 (Industrial). For LU1.2 and LU3, there is only one polygon for each class and both are misclassified as LU5 (Residential).

Figure 9. F1 score for each land use class by manual evaluation

DST-derived solutions for OCS-GE polygons are compared to the initial land use labels in the 2016 data set. The decision is classified into three cases: no update, enrichment, and change. According to this classification, five OCS-GE polygons are classified as no-update, 118 OCS-GE polygons are classified as change and 172 as enrichment, as shown in Figure 10. About 60% of the detected polygons are enriched from LU235 to LU2, LU3 or LU5.

Figure 10. Distribution of updating decisions obtained by applying the proposed workflow.

Examples are shown in Figure 11. OCS-GE and CDS polygons are represented in, respectively, light blue and green. The red dot represents the *in-situ* visited location. Google Maps in 2018 and a 2016 orthophoto from the French Geoportal (<https://www.geoportail.gouv.fr>) are used to make a visual comparison.

In Figure 11a, there is a CDS polygon (labelled as LU4.1 - Transportation network) within the OCS-GE polygon. The land use label for the OCS-GE polygon in the 2016 database is LU4.1.3 (Air transport) and the DST-derived solution is also LU4.1.3 (Air transport). Thus, the corresponding land use label in the database will not be updated. For the second example (see Figure 11b), the contribution from in-situ data indicates that the LU label for the OCS-GE polygon is LU5 (Residential) while the original attribute is LU235 (Industrial, Commercial and Services and Residential). Thus, the corresponding LU label is updated to LU5. Figure 11c illustrates an example where an initial OCS-GE polygon has LU equal to LU6.3 (Not currently used). There are two CDS polygons (LU5 Residential) indicating new residential buildings and one CDS polygon (LU4.1 Transportation network) representing infrastructure use. The DST-solution is LU5 (Residential). Finally, the corresponding LU class of the OCS-GE polygon will be changed from LU6.3 (Not currently used) to LU5 (Residential). What is interesting to note here is that even with incomplete information (only two new buildings and part of the road detected by the CDS), our approach is able to assign a change to the OCS-GE polygon.

There are some changes within an OCS-GE polygon that are not sufficient to alter its LU class. For the example shown in Figure 11d, there are six divided CDS polygons (LU2 Industrial) representing industrial use within the OCS-GE polygon having LU equal to LU6.3 (Not currently used). The DST-solution is LU2 (Industrial). By comparing the imagery in 2016 and 2018, one can see that only part of the area is changed, and the majority part is still tree-covered area. However, LU2 (Industrial) will be incorrectly assigned to this OCS-GE polygon according to the current workflow. This case shows that sometimes it is not sufficient to take into account only the thematic information but also the geometry. In this specific case, two solutions are possible. One is to modify the geometry of the OCS-GE having the LU6.3 label (Not currently used), i.e., the polygons should be divided into two polygons LU6.3 and LU2. The second is to compute the proportion of different usages (here LU2 Industrial and LU6.3 Not currently used) and decide the value with respect to the maximum proposition defined in the mapping rules specifications. For the first solution, survey intervention would be needed whereas for the second solution, topographic data should be used.

Figure 11. Examples of updating the 2016 OCS-GE data using citizen-contributed data. (a) No update; (b) enrichment; (c) change; (d) update error. Input data (on the left); 2016 orthophoto from French Geoportal (images in the middle); 2018 Google Maps (images on the right).

5 Discussion and future work

The purpose of this study was to use citizen-observed data to update authoritative LULC data. The proposed workflow integrates authoritative LULC data with heterogeneous citizen-observed data based on Dempster-Shafer theory. Citizen-observed data are independent data sets that allow beliefs to be modelled according to their accuracy and confidence. The results have demonstrated the potential of using citizen-observed data for updating authoritative LULC data. This study has also shown that the quality, the number of observations and the contributor's agreement are important aspects and should be carefully managed to improve the process.

The proposed workflow has several advantages with respect to the LULC data needs. One benefit is the management of data sets with time stamps as inputs to the workflow. Data sets can have different acquisition dates. In the Toulouse pilot, we focused on the authoritative LULC data that are planned to be produced every 3 years. However, the proposed workflow can also be adapted for higher temporal resolutions, e.g., every year. To implement this, the data sets input to the workflow would require a temporal selection of citizen-observed data.

A second benefit of the workflow is to be able to take into account information coming from different and heterogeneous data sources, which may contain contradicting realities in the field or even be incomplete. Logically, the observations coming from the *in-situ* citizen-observed data are more likely to be reliable as they are collected in the field with no technical filter. This must be balanced with a visibility mask or with the difficulty of interpretation of some land use and the match with the database mapping specifications. The automatic change detection service is efficient in processing time for providing alerts of potential changes. Nevertheless, potential changes need to be validated. Collaborative and multiple validations by photointerpretation, even if far from the field, are useful for determining both the veracity of the change and its type.

A third benefit is the scalability of the workflow. In this deliverable, the workflow is applied to LULC data produced by IGN-France and uses two citizen-observed data sets with observations about changes in the study area. Other sources of information can be easily added to the workflow such as topographic information, changes coming from image processing (e.g., Landsat images); the only condition that should be required is the independence of the sources. Moreover, the workflow can be easily adapted to update other authoritative vector LULC data by adjusting the pre-processing and filtering steps to better fit to the characteristics of the data.

There are limitations to the proposed approach with regards to the input data and the process. First, concerning the citizen-observed data, there is a limitation in the volume and the spatial distribution of external data sources. First, few data were collected in the 2018 campaign with respect to the spatial extent of the study area. Second, the detected changes (although a small number were detected) provided by the CDS were distributed across the whole study site. Double validation has been made on all the detected changes, so few multiple validations exist. However, the *in-situ* citizen-observed data were distributed in spatial clusters as citizens tend to stay in a limited area, especially when they are on foot. *In-situ* observation also takes time, because of travelling between targeted locations and for interpretation of

the LULC in the field. The quality of the citizen-observed data would also need to be considered by the workflow, not only by type of data like it is in the workflow presently with the use of belief functions, but also for each individual observation. The quality of citizen-derived data can be assessed using intrinsic or extrinsic indicators. For intrinsic indicators, some observations correspond to the same targeted LULC polygon, so it is possible to give a confidence value depending on the contributor's agreement. For extrinsic data quality assessment, authoritative (e.g., a quarry data set produced by local authorities) or VGI data (e.g., OSM) are not yet included in the workflow. The quality of citizen-observed data will be further studied and documented in deliverable D5.6.

Second, for the fusion process between pieces of information in the workflow, challenges concern mainly the mass of belief assessment. Sensitivity tests could be made in the future.

Another limit of the current workflow is the fact that the geometry of the LULC polygons is not modified. In the experiments, only the label of the OCS-GE polygon is modified, not its shape. Achieving this would require further research.

Future work is planned regarding the proposed workflow by integrating other data sets. These may come from images, from processing results, from VGI platforms and/or from existing authoritative databases.

Below is a list of potential future developments:

1. A series of campaigns will run in 2019 for the Toulouse pilot (see D2.2). These new data will complete the two data sources that are already used in the current workflow.
2. Introducing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) into the workflow. The idea is to infer LULC classes for the OCS-GE polygons to be updated by using information from adjacent polygons. The 2013 OCS-GE data have been used to train a multi-task CNN model, which can predict LU and LC simultaneously. The evaluation of the first results shows that the model performs well on the prediction of LU with an overall accuracy of 89%. For LC, the overall accuracy is only 78%. The model is then applied to OCS-GE 2016 polygons highlighted in the citizen-observed data as changed. The inferred LU classes from CNN outputs are regarded as a new data source in the workflow. The first tests showed that the CNN outputs can increase the mass of belief for the DST-derived solutions. For some cases, the CNN outputs can correct the final solution, which was affected by (divided) CDS polygons with small area values. However, we also observed that the CNN output can lead to incorrect final DST solutions when the CNN predictions are incorrect. Thus, how to properly assess the quality of the CNN results and integrate them into the workflow should be further explored.
3. Integration of the SPOTIT service proposed by IGN for detecting changes from SPOT images at different dates. These changes would be validated manually by contributors. Some changes may be interesting inputs to the workflow even if they are more related to LC change.
4. Integration of outcomes from the Termos internal IGN project about the use of deep learning to produce and update LULC data from remote sensing data. This is an on-going project although the intermediate results could potentially be integrated.
5. Integration of the classification results from the French Research ANR MAESTRIA project. In particular, ongoing experiments are focussing on the classification of SPOT-6/7 and Sentinel-2 images using deep learning approaches. Such classifications have been undertaken for the Toulouse study area recently

and should be integrated into the fusion process. This and the previous classification mostly correspond to LC maps (since LC nomenclature is more compatible with remote sensing approaches), but they can, nevertheless, reveal changes and help to better delineate them.

6. Integration of different releases of the topographic database produced by IGN-France with metric precision made on a continuous basis. The differences between the two releases of BD Topo can be used to identify the changes. Afterwards, these changes can be used as inputs to the workflow or to validate the final decisions from the DST in the fusion data process (no change, enrichment or change).

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Annex 1: Land Use and Land Cover Nomenclature

Land cover nomenclature

LC class	French	English
CS 1.1.1.1	Zones bâties	Built-up areas
CS 1.1.1.2	Zones non bâties	Non-built-up areas
CS 1.1.2.1	Zones à matériaux minéraux	Areas with mineral materials
CS 1.1.2.2	Zones à autres matériaux composites	Areas with other composite materials
CS 1.2.1	Sols nus	Bare soil
CS 1.2.2	Surfaces d'eau	Water
CS 1.2.3	Névés et glaciers	Snow and ice
CS 2.1.1.1	Peuplements de feuillus	Hardwood forest
CS 2.1.1.2	Peuplements de conifères	Coniferous forest
CS 2.1.1.3	Peuplements mixtes	Mixed forest
CS 2.1.2	Formations arbustives et sous-arbrisseaux	Shrubs
CS 2.1.3	Autres formations ligneuses	Other woody formations
CS 2.2.1	Formations herbacées	Herbaceous vegetation
CS 2.2.2	Autres formations non ligneuses	Other non-woody formations

Land use nomenclature

Land use class	French	English	Description
US1.1	Agriculture	Agriculture	This class includes cultivation (plants, mushrooms, etc.) and products of animal origin for direct feeding (for sale and for self-consumption) or indirect (industrial transfers). This class also includes areas dedicated to the cultivation of biofuels, open field growing areas and green areas.
US1.2	Sylviculture	Forestry	This class includes areas dedicated to wood production. This category also includes forestry activities leading to processed products such as firewood, charcoal wood and round used in a raw form (e.g., mine wood, wood crushing).
US1.3	Activités d'extraction	Mining and quarrying	This class comprises extractive activities of minerals and naturally occurring materials in solid form (coal, ores, gravel, sand, salt), liquids (petroleum), gas (natural gas) or biomass (peat).
US1.4	Pêche et aquaculture	Aquaculture and fishing	This category includes professional fishing and aquaculture.
US1.5	Autre	Other primary production	This class includes professional hunting, product collection growing wild, non-timber forest

			products and livestock rearing animals and any other primary production not listed above.
US2	Production secondaire: industriel	Secondary production: industriel	This class includes industrial and manufacturing activities that harness primary production for by manufacture products (e.g. food manufactory, textile, leather, wood, paper). It also includes storage and transportation areas directly related to the activities of manufacturing.
US3	Production tertiaire: Commercial et services	Tertiary production: Commercial et Services	This class includes areas where services are produced for other businesses, for consumers or citizens. It encompasses the wholesale and retail trade, repair services, hotels and restaurants, financial services, real estate, services to companies, rental services, public administration, advocacy and social security, education, health and social work and collective, social and personal services.
US4.1	Réseau de transport	Transportation network	This class contains all transportation networks
US4.1.1	Transport routier	Road transport	This class includes areas used for road transport (roads, car parks, petrol stations ...).
US4.1.2	Transport ferré	Railway transport	This class includes areas used for rail transport (rails, railway stations).
US4.1.3	Transport aérien	Air transport	This class includes areas used for air transport, airports and related services (tracks, infrastructures ...).
US4.1.4	Transport fluvial et maritime	Water transport	This class includes areas used for water transport (ports, rivers, docks and related services).
US4.1.5	Autres moyen de transport	Other means of transport	This class includes areas used for other transport infrastructure not included in classes 4.1.1 - 4.1.4.
US4.2	Services de logistique et de stockage	Logistics and storage	This class includes areas used for different storage services (not directly related to industry) and logistics services.
US4.3	Réseaux d'utilités publiques	Public utility networks	This class includes infrastructure utilities.
US5	Usage résidentiel	Residential	This class includes areas used primarily for dwelling. It includes houses, blocks of flats and mobile homes in cities, villages and rural areas if they are not related to primary production.
US235	Usage industriel, Commercial et Services, Résidentiel	Industrial, Commercial and services,	Areas having the use expressed in Land use classes LU2, LU3, and LU5. of the table.

		and Residential	
US6.1	Zones de transition (ou de construction)	Construction zones	This class includes areas under construction.
US6.2	Zones abandonnées (friches)	Abandoned areas	This class covers abandoned areas no matter the use: agricultural, residential and industrial, transport and basic infrastructure areas.
US6.3	Sans usage	Not currently used	This class includes natural areas without any economic use.
US6.4	Usage inconnu	Usage unknown	This class includes areas where land use is unknown.

Combination LU/LC classes

Land Cover		Land use												
CS 1.1.1.1	US1.1	US1.3	US2	US3	US4.1.1	US4.1.2	US4.1.3	US4.1.4	US4.1.5	US4.2	US4.3	US5	US6.1	US6.2
CS 1.1.1.2	US2	US3	US4.1.1	US4.1.2	US4.1.3	US4.1.4	US4.1.5	US4.2	US4.3	US5	US6.1	US6.2		
CS 1.1.2.1	US1.3	US4.1.1	US4.1.2	US4.1.3	US4.1.5	US5	US6.1	US6.2						
CS 1.1.2.2	US4.3	US6.2	US6.3	US6.4										
CS 1.2.1	US3.4.1	US3	US6.1	US6.2	US6.3	US6.4								
CS 1.2.2	US1.1	US1.3	US1.4	US2	US3.4.1	US3	US4.1.4	US6.3						
CS 1.2.3	US3	US6.3												
CS 2.1.1.1	US1.1	US1.2	US1.5	US5	US6.3	US6.4								
CS 2.1.1.2	US1.1	US1.2	US1.5	US5	US6.3	US6.4								
CS 2.1.1.3	US1.1	US1.2	US1.5	US5	US6.3	US6.4								
CS 2.1.2	US1.1	US4.2	US5	US6.3	US6.4									
CS 2.1.3	US1.1	US6.3	US6.4											
CS 2.2.1	US1.1	US3	US4.2	US5	US6.3	US6.4								
CS 2.2.2	US1.1	US4.2	US6.3	US6.4										